

Effect of pressure on the carbon dioxide hydrate – water interfacial free energy along its dissociation line

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We investigate the effect of pressure on the carbon dioxide (CO₂) hydrate–water interfacial free energy along its dissociation line using advanced computer simulation techniques. In previous works, we have determined the interfacial energy of the hydrate at 400 bar using the TIP4P/ice and TraPPE molecular models for water and CO₂, respectively, in combination with two different extensions of the Mold Integration technique [J. Chem. Phys. **141**, 134709 (2014)]. Results obtained from computer simulation, 29(2) and 30(2) mJ/m², are found to be in excellent agreement with the only two measurements that exist in the literature, 28(6) mJ/m² determined by Uchida *et al.* [J. Phys. Chem. B **106**, 8202 (2002)] and 30(3) mJ/m² by Anderson *et al.* [J. Phys. Chem. B **107**, 3507 (2002)]. Since the experiments do not allow to obtain the variation of the interfacial energy along the dissociation line of the hydrate, we extend our previous studies to quantify the effect of pressure on the interfacial energy at different pressures. Our results suggest that there exists a correlation between the interfacial free energy values and the pressure, i.e., it decreases with the pressure between 100 and 1000 bar. We expect that the combination of reliable molecular models and advanced simulation techniques could help to improve our knowledge of the thermodynamic parameters that control the interfacial free energy of hydrates from a molecular perspective.

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural gas hydrates are nonstoichiometric inclusion solid compounds in which guest molecules, such as methane (CH₄) or carbon dioxide (CO₂), are enclathrated in the voids left by a periodic network of water molecules (host). Small molecules, including CH₄ and CO₂, form type sI hydrates, while larger guests usually form type sII and type sH hydrate structures.¹ Applied research on hydrates has been motivated because these strategic materials are potential alternative sources of energy as CH₄ hydrate deposits,^{2,3} and also are important from their global climate impact,^{1–6} CO₂ sequestration^{7–9} and gas storage¹⁰ and transportation.^{11–13}

From a fundamental point of view, understanding hydrate growth and nucleation is a challenging task.¹ Although some research groups have published significant results on hydrate nucleation from a molecular perspective, the molecular mechanisms that control it are still poorly understood.^{14–21} In this context, some of us have recently published some seminal papers to study the thermodynamic and kinetic parameters that control nucleation of methane and CO₂ hydrates from a molecular perspective.^{22,23} One of these parameters is undeniably the interfacial free energy.²⁴ In this work, we concentrate on the determination of the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy from computer simulation.

Experimental, theoretical, and molecular simulation techniques for determining fluid–fluid interfacial tensions are well established.^{25–27} However, there is a rather limited number of methods to obtain interfacial free energies of solid–fluid systems, with particular emphasis on the hydrate–water interfacial free energy.^{25,28} In the case of CO₂ hydrates, only two independent sets of experiments exist in the literature. Uchida

*et al.*²⁹ and Anderson *et al.*³⁰ have obtained the interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate from indirect measurements of the hydrate dissociation temperature in porous materials with varying pore size combined with the use of the Gibbs–Thomson equation.^{29,31–35} The analysis of the experimental data assumes that interfacial energy does not vary along the dissociation line when the pressure is changed, providing a single value of the interfacial energy.^{29,30} In fact, the pressure dependence of the interfacial free energy is totally unknown experimentally and two important questions arise from these results after twenty years: (1) Does the interfacial free energy of a hydrate change along its dissociation line? And (2), if the answer to the former question is affirmative, how does the interfacial free energy vary along it?

Computer simulations of realistic models constitute an efficient alternative approach that can provide valuable information on hydrate–water interfacial energies from a microscopic point of view.¹ Very recently, we have determined the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial energy by combining reliable molecular models for water and carbon dioxide and advanced molecular simulation techniques.^{36,37} We have used two different but complementary extensions of the Mold Integration (MI) method proposed by Espinosa *et al.*³⁸ to determine the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy at 400 bar. Particularly, we have used the TIP4P/Ice³⁹ and TraPPE⁴⁰ molecular models for water and CO₂, respectively, that are able to describe very accurately the CO₂ hydrate dissociation line in a wide range of pressures.⁴¹ Calculations using the two extensions of the MI method also provide a good description of the interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate at 400 bar: 29(2) mJ/m² and 30(2) mJ/m² using the Mold Integration Host (MI–H)³⁶ and the Mold Integration Guest (MI–

G),³⁷ respectively. These results are in excellent agreement with the experimental data of Uchida *et al.*²⁹ and Anderson *et al.*³⁰ for the interfacial energy, 26(8) and 30(3) mJ/m².

In this work, we study the dependence of the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy, γ_{hw} with the pressure along the three–phase coexistence line of the hydrate. We determine γ_{hw} at different pressures using the MI–H technique and the same molecular models for water and CO₂ as in our previous works. It is important to remark that this election allows to describe very accurately the CO₂ hydrate dissociation line in a wide range of pressures, including the pressures considered in this study, and it provides an excellent description of the interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate at 400 bar.

The organization of this paper is as follows: In Sec. II, we describe the methodology used in this work. Molecular simulation details are presented in Sec. III. The results obtained in this work are described in Sec. IV. Finally, conclusions are presented in Sec. V.

II. METHODOLOGY

The interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate is calculated using the MI–H methodology proposed by Algaba *et al.*,³⁶ based on the original MI method proposed by Espinosa and collaborators.³⁸ The method, which can be only applied at coexistence conditions, is based on the use of a mold of square-well interacting sites located in a lattice of one or several crystalline planes of the solid phase involved in the calculation of the interfacial energy.^{38,42,43} The mold can be switched on gradually to induce the formation of a solid slab in the fluid at coexistence conditions. This allows to evaluate the difference in free energy between the fluid and the fluid with the solid slab induced by the mold via thermodynamic integration. According to the method,^{36,38} the work needed to form the thin crystal slab of the solid phase in the fluid phase can be computed by integrating the average number of filled wells, $N_{fw}(\varepsilon)$, along the thermodynamic path linking both phases,

$$\Delta G^{hw} = N_w \varepsilon_m - \int_0^{\varepsilon_m} \langle N_{fw}(\varepsilon) \rangle_{NP_z, \mathcal{A}T} d\varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where N_w is the number of wells in the mold, ε is the well depth, and ε_m is the maximum well depth. The average number of the filled wells is obtained in the isothermal-isobaric ensemble to ensure that the system is always at the selected coexistence conditions. \mathcal{A} represents the interfacial area between the hydrate and the aqueous solution of CO₂. In the isothermal-isobaric ensemble simulations used in this work, only fluctuations of the side perpendicular to the interface are allowed. Note that we have subtracted $-N_w \varepsilon_m$, the extra energy supplied to the system to induce the formation of the crystal slab. According to this, ΔG^{hw} represents the reversible work needed to create the slab and it allows the computation of the solid–fluid interfacial free energy in a straightforward fashion.

The success of the MI methodology depends on the election of several parameters that determine the final value of the

interfacial free energy: the range of the square-well interaction sites of the mold, r_w , the number and distribution of the wells in the fluid phase, N_w , and the value of the maximum well depth, ε_m . In addition to that, the preparation of the initial simulation box is key since it determines if the system is at coexistence conditions when the integral in Eq. (1) is calculated. When r_w is equal to the so-called optimal value,³⁸ r_w^0 , ΔG^{hw} and the solid–fluid interfacial free energy, γ_{hw} , are related in a simple way,

$$\gamma_{hw} = \frac{\Delta G^{hw}}{2\mathcal{A}} \quad (2)$$

Factor 2 arises because two crystal–fluid interfaces appear when the solid slab is induced. In this work, we use the MI–H method to evaluate the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy. Since we use the MI–H method, the wells of the mold are located at the equilibrium crystallographic positions of the oxygen atoms of the water molecules of one layer of the sI structure of the hydrate.³⁶ The rest of the technical details of the methodology, the preparation of the initial simulation boxes, and how the number of wells and layers, the maximum value of ε , and the optimal value r_w^0 are similar to those used in our seminal work.³⁶

III. SIMULATION DETAILS

We use the GROMACS simulation package⁴⁴ to perform MD simulations via the $NP_{\mathcal{A}T}$ or isothermal-isobaric ensemble^{27,45} at 100, 400, and 1000 bar using the MI–H technique. Water and CO₂ molecules are modelled using the well-known TIP4P/Ice³⁹ and TraPPE⁴⁰ molecular models, respectively. We also use a modified Berthelot rule proposed by Míguez *et al.*⁴¹ Particularly, we use $\varepsilon_{12} = \xi_{12} (\varepsilon_{11} \varepsilon_{22})^{1/2}$, with $\xi_{12} = 1.13$ for the unlike Lennard-Jones interactions between CO₂ and water. The main reason for using this approach is to be consistent with our previous works^{36,37} when comparing interfacial free energy values. Although this election overestimates the solubility of CO₂ in water, it provides an excellent estimation of the dissociation temperature of the CO₂ hydrate, T_3 , along the whole dissociation line. The simulation box is a parallelepiped of volume $V = L_x \times L_y \times L_z$, with L_x , L_y , and L_z the dimensions of the simulation box. L_x and L_y are kept constant and only L_z is varied along the simulation. This ensures that the system is under the equilibrium normal pressure (perpendicular to the hydrate slab formed when the mold is switched on). To avoid stress in the slab of the CO₂ hydrate when the mold is switched on, we first simulate bulk solid phases using the anisotropic version of the NPT ensemble to determine the equilibrium L_x and L_y dimensions of the simulation box. This ensures that the slabs simulated, at the equilibrium pressures, are non-stressed.^{46–48}

To be consistent with our previous works,^{36,37,41} the initial simulation boxes used in this work are prepared in an identical way. We use 736 water molecules surrounded by two pure liquid slabs formed each of them by 128 CO₂ molecules. Dimensions of the simulation boxes along the x and y -axis parallel

to the water-CO₂ planar interface are chosen to be consistent with the size of the hydrate unit cell formed when the mold is switched on. We also use $N_w = 48$ attractive sites, with $\epsilon_m = 8k_B T$, to induce the formation of the hydrate slab in the simulation box at the three pressures. An image of the initial configuration can be visualized in the supplementary material (multimedia files). The first frame of each movie corresponds to the initial configuration generated as explained previously.

Newton's equations are solved using a Verlet leapfrog algorithm⁴⁹ with a time step of 0.002 ps. All simulations are run at constant temperature and pressure using a Nosé-Hoover thermostat⁵⁰ and a Parrinello-Rahman barostat.⁵¹ Simulations of the bulk solid phase to determine the equilibrium dimensions of the simulation box are run using the anisotropic version of the Parrinello-Rahman barostat. Relaxation times used in the thermostat and barostat are 2 and 1 ps, respectively. Long-range interactions due to electrostatic interactions are determined using the Particle Mesh Ewald technique.⁵² We use a cutoff radius for both dispersive interactions and the real part of electrostatic interactions of 10 Å. Note that this cutoff distance is the same as that used in our previous works^{36,37,41} and will allow to compare the results obtained with full consistency. No long range corrections were used in our study. LINCS algorithm is used in order to keep the molecular geometry. For an account of some additional simulation details, we recommend the revision of our previous work.³⁶

IV. RESULTS

In order to find r_w^0 at different pressures, we run several simulations for different well radii and follow the evolution of n_h , the number of water molecules in the solid phase, when the mold is switched on at the beginning of the simulations. All of them start from a configuration of the CO₂ solution, at the appropriate concentration depending on the pressure, in contact with a reservoir of a pure CO₂ liquid phase as explained in the previous section. The number of water molecules forming the hydrate slab is calculated using rotational invariant local bond order parameters to distinguish between fluid-like and solid-like particles. We follow our previous works^{36,37} and consider the combination of the \bar{q}_3 and \bar{q}_6 averaged order parameters proposed by Lechner and Dellago⁵³ to discriminate between fluid-like and solid-like water molecules during our simulations. All the details of the parameter used in this work to identify water molecules can be found in our previous papers.^{36,37} We monitor $n_h = n_h(t)$ and identify the values of r_w for which the curves do not exhibit an induction period and the hydrate grows, and those for which n_h exhibits some induction period. The optimal value r_w^0 , for each pressure, is enclosed between the two values for which the hydrate grows or does not grow.^{36–38}

Fig. 1 shows the evolution of n_h , as a function of time, of two representative values of r_w for each pressure. As can be seen, for low values of r_w the hydrate phase grows with no induction period in all trajectories. However, for high values of r_w the hydrate does not grow. To determine the optimal values of r_w it is necessary to get a more complete picture of the be-

FIG. 1. Number of water molecules in the hydrate slab, n_h as a function of time for several trajectories and different well radius r_w (as indicated in the legends). Simulations are performed using $\epsilon = 8k_B T$ and at coexistence conditions: 100 bar and 284 K (upper panels), 400 bar and 287 K (middle panels), and 1000 bar and 289 K (bottom panels). Each color represents an independent trajectory generated using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration.

havior of n_h , as a function of time, exploring several values of r_w . A complete representation of all the trajectories analyzed in this work (between 12 and 19 different r_w values depending on the pressure considered) is presented in the supplementary material.

It is not easy to determine precisely the optimal values of r_w^0 for hydrates. We follow here the criteria previously established by us in our previous works.^{36,37} Particularly, at 1000 bar, we find that $r_w = 0.950$ Å is the highest r_w value for which none of the trajectories shows an induction period. For $r_w = 0.982$ Å, at least one trajectory exhibits an induction period (see the supplementary material). Following the nomenclature used in our previous works,^{36,37} we name these values as lower and upper bounds for r_w^0 , $r_w^{(l)} = 0.950$ Å and $r_w^{(u)} = 0.982$ Å. According to this, the optimal value at 1000 bar is $r_w^0 = (r_w^{(u)} + r_w^{(l)})/2 \approx 0.966$ Å. As in our previous works, it is necessary to provide enough uncertainty to this value, which allows to give the appropriate confidence interval to r_w^0 and γ_{hw} . The uncertainty assigned to r_w^0 at this pressure is 0.08 Å, and the final value at 1000 bar is $r_w^0 = 0.97(8)$ Å.

FIG. 2. The average number of filled wells, $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z, \mathcal{A}T}$, as a function of the well depth ϵ , at 100bar for the principal plane of the CO₂ hydrate. The radius of the mold used is $r_w = 1.140 \text{ \AA}$. The circles correspond to the values obtained from $NP_z, \mathcal{A}T$ simulations of 40ns and the blue curve represents its corresponding fit. The inset represents the fits of the average number of filled wells using well radii higher than the optimal value, $r_w = 1.140$ (blue), 1.172 (black), 1.203 (red), and 1.235 \AA (green).

Following the same approach for the rest of pressures, we find that $r_w^0 = 0.94(8)$ and $0.84(8) \text{ \AA}$ for 400 and 100bar, respectively. See the complete series of r_w values explored in this work in the supplementary material.

Once the optimal values r_w^0 for each pressure have been determined, it is possible to calculate γ_{hw} for several values $r_w > r_w^0$. Particularly, we use four different values of r_w at each pressure to calculate the integral in Eq. (1). This is done by determining the average number of filled wells with water molecules for a given number of ϵ values. Fig. 2 shows $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z, \mathcal{A}T}$, as a function of ϵ , at 100bar using a value $r_w = 1.140 \text{ \AA}$. We have also considered other values of the potential range of the wells, $r_w = 1.172, 1.203, \text{ and } 1.235 \text{ \AA}$, shown in the inset of Fig. 2. Note that different values for r_w give slightly different filling curves. All these values are larger than the optimal value to ensure that the states visited by the system during the simulations correspond to liquid states. With this election, the integration of Eq. (1) is always reversible. Note that $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z, \mathcal{A}T}$, as a function of time, behaves smoothly and it reaches the expected plateau value ($N_{fw} \rightarrow N_w$) when $\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_m$. Finally, we have also checked that all the wells of the mold are fully occupied with only one water molecule for all the values of ϵ used for the integration. The rest of the filling curves corresponding to our calculations at 400 and 1000bar are presented in the supplementary material.

The CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy values, for each pressure and different choices of r_w , can be readily obtained by integrating the corresponding $\langle N_{fw}(\epsilon) \rangle_{NP_z, \mathcal{A}T}$ functions with respect to ϵ according to Eq. (1) and using Eq. (2). The results obtained are shown in Fig. 3. As can be seen, the

FIG. 3. CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy as a function of the potential well radius of the mold as obtained from the MI–H methodology at 100 (open green circles), 400 (open blue circles), and 1000bar (open red circles). The dashed lines represent linear fits of each date at the corresponding pressure, the open squares the interfacial tensions evaluated at the lower and upper bounds of r_w^0 , $r_w^{(l)}$ and $r_w^{(u)}$, at each pressure, and the open diamonds the extrapolation of the linear fit to the optimal well radius at the corresponding pressure.

interfacial free energy values for each pressure (open circles) follow a linear behavior with r_w , in agreement with previous results.^{36–38,43} We also perform linear fits of the γ_{hw} values (for $r_w < r_w^0$), at each pressure, to obtain the value of the interfacial energy evaluated at each optimal value r_w^0 . Following our previous works, we have estimated the uncertainties of γ_{hw} at each pressure from the uncertainties of r_w^0 . Particularly, the error associated with each value of γ_{hw} is half of the difference between the values of the interfacial energy evaluated at the lower and upper bounds of r_w around each optimal value (open squares).

The interfacial free energy value that we obtain in this work at 400bar, using $N_w = 48$ wells for the mold, $31(2) \text{ mJ/m}^2$, is fully consistent with those obtained in our previous works,^{36,37} $29(2) \text{ mJ/m}^2$ and $30(2) \text{ mJ/m}^2$. According to this, we obtain the same value of the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial energy within the error bars. This result is especially interesting since we have previously used two different versions of the method and different number of wells, the MI–H method with $N_w = 56$ sites for water molecules and the MI–G technique with $N_w = 16$ sites for the CO₂ molecules. The interfacial free energy values at 100 and 1000bar are $33(2)$ and $30(2) \text{ mJ/m}^2$, respectively. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time the interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate–water interface is determined from computer simulation along its dissociation line.

It is also interesting to compare the interfacial energy values for varying pressure with the experimental data of Uchida *et al.*²⁹ and Anderson *et al.*³⁰ obtained independently several years ago. Our results for γ_{hw} , at the three pressures, agree very well with the value proposed by Uchida and collabora-

FIG. 4. CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy as a function of pressure along its dissociation line as obtained from the MI–H methodology. The dotted curve is a guide to the eye.

tors, 28(6) mJ/m², and also with those measured by Anderson and coworkers, 30(3) mJ/m². We should notice that error bars are large, not only for the experimental values, 6 and 3 mJ/m², but also for the simulation data obtained in this work, 2 mJ/m². A first analysis of the results seems to indicate that the interfacial free energy is constant in a wide range of pressures, between 100 and 1000 bar. This is in agreement with the data provided by Uchida *et al.*²⁹ and Anderson *et al.*³⁰ if we take into account that all the results are within the error bars. However, is the interfacial free energy of a hydrate constant along its dissociation line?

The experimental data taken from the literature were published without specifying the pressures at which γ_{hw} values were obtained.^{29,30} More precisely, the authors estimated the interfacial free energy of the CO₂ hydrate from pressure-temperature dissociation experimental data measured in porous materials combined with the phenomenological Gibbs-Thomson equation.^{31,33,34} They assumed, among other approximations, that the interfacial free energy is constant and it only depends on the mean diameter of the pores. According to this, the hydrate interfacial free energy does not vary with the pressure. In other words, as it is mentioned in the Introduction, the dependence of γ_{hw} with pressure is not known experimentally.

However, the technique used in this work allows to obtain γ_{hw} at different pressures along the hydrate dissociation line at coexistence conditions. We have represented the interfacial free energy as a function of pressure in Fig. 4. As can be seen, our results suggest that there is a weak correlation between the interfacial energy values and the pressure, i.e., γ_{hw} decreases with pressure along the dissociation line. To the best of our knowledge, this behavior has not been previously reported in the literature and it is a surprising result. The dependence of the solid-liquid interfacial free energy with pressure has been

studied in the literature by two groups in two different systems. On one hand, Laird *et al.* have determined the solid-liquid interfacial free energy along the coexistence line of the Lennard-Jones (LJ) system using Gibbs-Cahn integration.⁵⁴ On the other hand, Espinosa *et al.* have calculated the water–Ih ice interfacial free energy at two different pressures, 1 and 2000 bar, on the melting line of Ih ice, using the original MI method.^{43,55} Although the pressure–temperature slope of the corresponding coexistence lines have different sign (in the LJ system the slope is positive and in the water case is negative), in both cases the interfacial free energy increases with pressure. This behavior is contrary to that observed in the case of the CO₂ hydrate. Note that the dissociation line of the CO₂ hydrate exhibits a positive slope in the range of pressures studied in this work.

It would be interesting to explain this behavior from a molecular perspective. In the case of the water–Ih ice interface, Espinosa and coworkers⁵⁵ proposed that the interfacial energy increase could be due to the breakage of hydrogen bonds in the liquid phase. It seems this is not the case for the CO₂ hydrate. However, this is not a definitive conclusion. The error bars associated to the experimental measurements are large, as well as those corresponding to the simulation data. A more detailed study would provide additional information on the behavior of the CO₂ hydrate interfacial free energy as a function of the pressure along its dissociation line.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We have analyzed the effect of pressure on the CO₂ hydrate–water interfacial free energy along its dissociation line from MD computer simulations. We have used the TraPPE force field to model CO₂ molecules and the TIP4P/Ice model to describe H₂O molecules. This election allows to describe very accurately the CO₂ hydrate dissociation line in a wide range of pressures, including the pressures considered in this study.

In two previous papers, we have used the same models and two extensions of the original MI methodology to account for the interfacial energy of the CO₂ hydrate at 400 bar. These techniques, which allow to calculate the free energy at coexistence conditions, are based on the definition of the interfacial free energy and well-established tools from Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics. In this work, we use one of the extensions, the co-called MI–H technique, to determine the interfacial free energy at three different pressures along the dissociation line, 100, 400, and 1000 bar.

The interfacial free energy value obtained at 400 bar, 31(2) mJ/m², is fully consistent with those obtained previously using two independent versions of the method, 29(2) and 30(2) mJ/m². We also obtain similar values of the interfacial energy at 100 and 1000 bar, 33(2) and 30(2) mJ/m², respectively. All the results are consistent and agree very well with the experimental values taken from the literature, 28(6) and 30(3) mJ/m².

The results obtained seem to indicate in a first analysis that the interfacial free energy is constant in a wide range of pres-

tures, in agreement with the results provided by experiments. Unfortunately, the experimental technique assumes that the interfacial energies are independent of the pressure. Contrarily, the MI–H and MI–G methods allow to determine the interfacial free energy at different thermodynamic conditions at co-existence. A more careful analysis of the results suggests that there is a weak correlation between the interfacial free energy values and the pressure, i.e., γ_{hw} decreases with the pressure. This is not a definitive conclusion since the error bars associated with the experimental measurements are large, as well as those corresponding to the simulation data, and our study has been performed in a limited range of pressures, between 100 and 1000 bar. Although a more detailed analysis is needed to confirm the main result of this study, this work corroborates that the combination of the TIP4P/ice and TraPPE models and the MI methodology is a powerful and valuable approach for calculating interfacial free energies of CO₂ hydrates.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

See the supplementary material for the time evolution of the number of water molecules in the CO₂ hydrate slab for the different well radii and pressures considered, the filling curves calculated at 400 and 1000 bar, and the multimedia results (movies) obtained from MD computer simulations showing crystallization and no crystallization starting from an equilibrated liquid–liquid configuration of the CO₂ + H₂O binary mixture.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflicts to disclose.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Cristóbal Romero-Guzmán: Visualization (lead); Methodology (equal); Investigation (lead); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Iván M. Zerón:** Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **José Manuel Míguez:** Validation (lead); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Bruno Mendiboure:** Formal analysis (lead); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

Jesús Algaba: Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Felipe J. Blas:** Conceptualization (lead); Funding acquisition (lead); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available within the article and its supplementary material.

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